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Impact Of School Learning Environment On Students' Dropout In Public Secondary Schools In Rivers State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of the school learning environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 311 public senior secondary schools in 23 LGAs in the state of Rivers, from which 380 were sampled through a stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire, titled, "School Learning Environment on Students Dropout Questionnaire. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while the hypothesis was analyzed using Z-test statistics at a 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed that school physical environment, and school academic environment, had an impact on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria It was also found that teachers' perception of the impact of school physical and academic environments on students' dropout was not significantly dependent on students' Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the school physical environment in Rivers State should be improved by renovating and repainting old and dilapidated classroom buildings and adequate facilities provided to make the schools more attractive and conducive for learning. In addition, the academic environment of the school should be free from abuse and violence. Finally, it was recommended that the school's academic environment should be improved by monitoring teachers' classroom management and Instructional delivery.

Keywords: Dropout, Environment, School physical environment, School social environment, Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

The educational framework in Nigeria is deeply rooted in the idea that education is fundamental for driving national progress. It is guided by two main principles: incorporating individuals into active and responsible citizens and ensuring equal educational opportunities for all citizens at the primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of education, both within and outside the formal school setting. As a result, secondary education plays a pivotal role in the Nigerian education system. It is highly esteemed not only as a legitimate qualification for desirable employment but also as a pathway to higher education. Against this backdrop, the Universal Basic Education (UBE) was introduced in the country. In 2004, the Federal Government of Nigeria enacted the UBE law to guarantee that children complete full primary school and achieve the important objectives outlined in the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS), which include wealth creation, job opportunities, poverty reduction, and realignment of values (International Monetary Fund-IMF, 2005). The UBE program aims to improve access to education and reduce student dropout rates. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2015), a student who discontinues education before completing the program is classified as a dropout. Dropout, in a broader sense, refers to a student

who, for various reasons, did not complete the level of education the student initially enrolled in (Dekkers and Claassen, 2011). Dropout represents a misuse of government initiatives, such as teacher training, school and classroom construction, provision of seats, teaching aids, books, free meals, footwear, and more, as it results in underutilizing government efforts. This challenge has become deeply entrenched within our educational system, as failing to complete secondary school not only limits future opportunities for higher education but also significantly depletes the already scarce resources the government allocates for delivering quality education.

The reworded text provides a comprehensive insight into the challenges faced by educational institutions in certain regions of Rivers State. Despite efforts to promote sustainable educational participation, the region continues to grapple with high dropout rates among young individuals. These dropouts are primarily attributed to personal reasons, resulting in the lack of fundamental knowledge and life skills, ultimately contributing to an increase in the crime rate. Specifically, male students are drawn to the allure of quick earnings through engagement in oil bunkering, while female students often leave due to early marriage or pregnancy.

The physical school environment, such as the infrastructure, buildings, grounds, and playgrounds, as well as factors like lighting, background noise, air quality, and thermal comfort, all contribute to the overall climate for learning. The government of Rivers State has taken active measures to improve the physical school environment by constructing new schools, renovating school structures, and providing necessary resources to ensure quality education. Their efforts aim to create a safe, clean, and comfortable learning environment for students. The research by Chukwuemeka and Agbara (2010) emphasizes the influence of family-related issues, school environment, societal pressures, and delayed social and economic benefits of education on high dropout rates in Nigerian schools. This study focuses on the impact of the school environment on student dropout rates, with "environment" encompassing internal and external conditions and influences affecting student life and development. The school's physical, social, and academic atmosphere plays a significant role in influencing student learning. The physical environment of the school refers to the school's physical facilities, which include; school buildings, equipment, Lawns, playground, lighting, ambient noise, indoor air quality, and/or thermal comfort of the physical building of the school and its location within a community. The physical environment of the school spells' out how safe, clean, and comfortable the surrounding offers a positive school climate in which students can learn. In Rivers State, the government has made concerted efforts to improve the school's physical environment by way of providing structures through building new schools, rebuilding and reconstructing dilapidated schools, training teachers, providing seats, teaching aids, books, and a lot more in a bid to provide quality education for her citizens.

The social setting at a school encompasses the various ways in which the school environment influences interactions between teachers and students, students with each other, teachers among themselves, teachers and school administration, students and school administration, and even interactions between parents and school staff. When students perceive their teacher(s) and the entire school system as supportive, they exhibit greater interest, value, effort, and enjoyment in their schoolwork (Fraser and Fisher, 2012). Education is an essential factor for the effective development of any country like Nigeria. The quality of education not only depends on teachers as reflected in the performance of their duties but also the effective coordination of the school environment. Environmental influence before now has not been considered as one of the factors that affect academic performance in secondary schools, hence, it has little or no attention in educational discourse and consideration. However, the school environment remains an important area that should be studied and well-managed to enhance students' academic performance. The issue of poor academic performance of students in Nigeria has been of much concern to the government, parents, teachers, and even students themselves. Ajao (2011) believes that a school with an adequate learning environment contributes to stirring up expected outcomes of learning that will facilitate good academic performance, by encouraging effective teaching and learning.

The government and especially parents are very much concerned with the quality and volume of learning acquired by their children, wards, and citizens as this is related to the quality and quantity of the contribution that an individual can make to his immediate family, community, and the nation as a whole (Thorndike, 2013). When a school fails to provide the necessary learning facilities and a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning to take place, it will be difficult for optimal

achievement of both teachers and students. Tsavga (2011) maintains that a learning environment plays a vital role in determining how students perform or respond to circumstances and situations around them. This implies that no society is void of environmental influences. The learning environment determines to a large extent how a student behaves and interacts, that is to say, the environment in which we find ourselves tends to mold our behaviour to meet the demands of life whether negatively or positively. School dropout can be influenced by gender-specific issues, as both boys and girls may have distinct reasons for leaving school. Some researchers consider school dropout as a gender-specific social issue (Khan, Tahir, and Shah, 2011; Taddese and Tadele, 2019) due to varying perceptions of male and female students in schools. For instance, male students might feel undervalued or believe they are not benefiting from school, choosing to drop out to pursue earning opportunities with their peers. Conversely, females may find certain physical tasks at school too challenging and decide to leave.

Statement of the Problem

The school environment is of paramount importance in shaping and reshaping intellectual ability. However, a supportive and favourable school environment enriched with enough learning facilities and a favourable climate makes students more comfortable, and more concentrated on their academic activities which results in high academic performance. Rivers State presents a concerning scenario where numerous young boys and girls lack the essential knowledge and life skills needed to support themselves. This unfortunate situation has led to a surge in crime rates, inter-ethnic tensions, and the intimidation of potential investors. Despite the government's efforts to keep students in schools, many children and youths in Rivers State can be seen selling goods or loitering on the streets, while some have become involved in cultism, militancy, and oil bunkering instead of pursuing education. Although student dropout rates have been linked to various factors such as family-related issues, societal pressures, and delayed rewards for education, it's imperative to examine whether school-related factors contribute to this trend.

Aim and objectives

The study aimed to investigate the influence of school learning environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objective of this study is to:

1. find out the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. determine the extent social environment influences students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of the school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does the school social environment influence students' drop out of public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female teachers on the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings score of male and female teachers on the extent the school social environment influences students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The school's physical surroundings significantly contribute to its overall value (Okoth, 2016). Rahmawati & Armida (2019) argue that the physical environment can either positively or negatively impact the performance of school administrators. It encompasses buildings, classrooms, furniture, equipment, teaching materials, laboratories, libraries, playgrounds, and more (Ayers, 2013). Other elements include walls, machinery, decorative items, playgrounds, skating rinks, swimming pools, and audiovisual equipment. Educational planners are more focused on aspects like the number of schools, teachers, and student facilities such as classrooms and school buildings, often overlooking environmental quality. The design and structure of the school environment form its physical

appearance, which influences the initial assessment of its quality by parents and friends of the educational institution. These factors collectively shape perceptions and preferences for desired learning experiences among parents and students. The learning environment is considered a crucial prerequisite for the effective functioning of the teaching and learning processes, as students' study habits are closely linked to it. Gros (2016) emphasizes that the learning environment significantly impacts the efficiency of learning time and identifies noise, distractions, lighting, temperature, cleanliness, comfort, and equipment as potential influencers of study habits. Ade, Nagaraj, & Vallepalli (2020) support this by stating that schools play a crucial role in providing a clean learning environment and proper water sanitation. Additionally, schools offer an ideal setting to help children cultivate beneficial habits for their future. However, managing the school environment has been a significant challenge for governments, school principals, and administrators over the years, encompassing issues such as location, aesthetics, waste management, sanitation, and more. School environments are often poorly maintained, with littered areas, dusty classrooms, inadequate ventilation, and neglected gardens for recess. A clean environment is essential for stimulating learning and intellectual development. The quality of the learning environment has received little attention, possibly due to insufficient information about its role in enhancing learning and intellectual development. Further concerns include the condition of libraries for reading and writing, which are often subpar, as well as flooded toilets and school management with unpleasant odors that can hinder the learning process.

Felix (2013) conducted a study on how the school environment affects the management of secondary school education. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. A survey design was used, and the sample consisted of 400 teachers from 20 grant-aided secondary schools in the Markurdi Metropolis of Benue state. The respondents were selected using a simple random sampling technique. Researchers created a 10-item four-point rating scale questionnaire called the 'Influence of School Environment on Management of Secondary School Questionnaire' (ISEMSSQ) to collect data. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation to address research questions, and the chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit was used to test the hypotheses at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The study found a significant influence of leadership style and school-community relations on secondary schools in the Makurdi metropolis of Benue state. The study recommended that school heads or administrators choose the most appropriate leadership style based on the school situation for effective management and that school host communities be involved in the operation of schools, especially in matters concerning students' welfare.

In Mamingot's (2020) study, the focus was on investigating school environmental management strategies in secondary schools in West Java. To conduct the study, three research questions were formulated. This involved the administration of a structured questionnaire to a random sample of 100 students in a school. The results revealed that strategies such as regular lawn cleaning, sweeping and painting of the school complex, landscaping and flower planting, good drainage, and proper garbage disposal are implemented to manage school environments. Challenges identified in the management of the school environment include the absence of gardeners for maintaining the school complex, erosion, lack of responsiveness from students and teachers towards environmental issues, difficulties in instilling environmental values in students due to varying home care practices, inadequate funds for procuring work tools/equipment, and challenges in waste disposal. To promote a better school environment conducive to academic excellence, the school environmental management team recommends planning for drainage and waste disposal, considering school locations for new schools, conducting janitorial work, organizing orientation programs, developing curricula on environmental management, carrying out inspections, and hosting school competitions and awards.

The research is focused on understanding the reasons behind students dropping out of school, particularly about the school environment. The study is based on Vincent Tinto's (1975) Student Integration and Institutional Departure Models. According to the theory, students enter college with certain family and personal characteristics, as well as pre-college education. They come with specific commitments to completing college and staying at their institution. Upon entering the educational system, they encounter academic challenges and intellectual growth, which contribute to their academic integration. Additionally, they become part of a social system where interactions with peers

and school activities lead to social integration. Tinto's models explain student retention and indicate that a student's sense of academic and social connectedness significantly influences their decision to stay in school and graduate. Therefore, the process of school dropout is viewed as a result of a combination of student traits and the extent of their academic, environmental, and social integration in school over an extended period. This theory is particularly relevant as it aims to elucidate how the physical, social, and academic school environment impacts students' decisions to remain in school over time.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 7,142 teachers in two hundred and seventy-six (276) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size for this study was three hundred and eighty (380) respondents, this was generated using the Taro Yamane formula. Stratified sampling techniques were considered suitable. A self-developed instrument was used for the collection of data. The instrument is titled, "Impact of School Learning Environment on Students' Dropout Questionnaire (ISLESDQ)". It was designed on a modified 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) is 4 points, Agree (A) is 3 points, Disagree (D) is 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) is 1 point. The instrument was validated by experts from Educational Measurement and Evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined by the use of the Cronbach Alpha formula. A reliability coefficient of 0.95 was obtained which was considered reliable and adequate for the study. Three hundred and eighty (380) copies of the questionnaire were distributed by the researcher and 275 copies were retrieved making up 89.3% respectively. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research questions. The level of rejection or acceptance of the null hypothesis is dependent on z- calculated value. Items with z-calculated values greater than the z-critical were rejected, while those with z-critical values less than the z-critical value were accepted. The null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using z-test statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the impact of the school's physical environment on students' dropout in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the impact of the school physical environment on students' dropout in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

SN	Physical Environment Variable	Respondents				Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Male = 163		Female =212			
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂		
1	The fence in my school is not good, so students move out freely and get in contact with bad people that may influence them to drop out.	3.42	0.49	3.44	0.49	3.43	Agree
2	Inadequate classrooms and Lockers/chairs may affect student learning thereby leading to failure and dropout.	3.10	0.63	2.01	0.62	2.55	Agree
3	The dilapidated nature of my school buildings may make students perform poorly and so drop out of school.	3.26	0.43	3.24	0.47	3.25	Agree
4	Poor ventilation in my classroom caused teachers and students.	3.32	0.69	3.23	0.74	3.27	Agree
5	The unkempt school physical environment is a great threat to students' safety.	2.98	0.84	2.94	0.80	2.96	Agree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.21	0.61	2.97	0.62	3.09	

Data in Table 4.1: presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the impact of the school physical environment on students' dropout in public senior secondary

schools in Rivers State. The results from item number 1 to 5, having the highest score in serial number 1 with 3.43 and lowest in item number 2 with 2.55, the average mean scores for the male and female are 3.21 and 2.97, respectively. Based on the average mean set score of 3.09 which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it implies that both male and female respondents agree on items 1 to 5 as the impact of the school physical environment on students' dropout in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question Two: *What is the influence of school social environment on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 4.2: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the influence of school social environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

SN	Social Environment variable	Respondents				Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Male = 163 X ₁ SD ₁		Female = 212 X ₂ SD ₂			
6	One of the reasons why students think of leaving the school is the issue of cultism in the school among students.	2.96	0.87	2.82	0.90	2.78	Agree
7	The aggressiveness of our teachers makes students absent from the classroom at times causing poor performance which leads to dropouts.	2.48	0.93	2.42	0.92	2.45	Disagree
8	The negative attitude of some teachers in my school could make students drop out of school.	2.68	0.91	2.66	0.90	2.67	Agree
9	Lack of social activities in my school could lead to dropout.	2.56	0.89	2.44	0.86	2.50	Agree
10	corporate punishment may scare some students and so cause them to drop out of school.	2.72	0.85	2.72	0.86	2.72	Agree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.68	0.89	2.61	0.88	2.62	

Data in Table 4.2 presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female respondents on the influence of school social environment on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State. The results from item number 6 to 10, having the highest score in item number 6 with 2.78 and lowest in item number 7 with 2.45, the average mean scores for the male and female are 2.68 and 2.61 respectively. Based on the average means score of 2.62 which is above the criterion mean score of 2.50, it implies that both male and female respondents agreed on items 6, 8, 9, and 10 as the influence of school social environment on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State. However, the male and female respondents disagree with item 7 as not part of the influence of school social environment on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female teachers on the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.3: z-test analysis on the difference between the mean rating score of male and female teachers on the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	163	3.21	0.61	373	3.756	±1.96	Not Significant
Female	212	2.97	0.62	2			Reject H ₀₁ (z-cal.< z-crit.)
Total	375			375			

Table 4.3 uncovered that males have mean and standard deviation scores of 3.21 and 0.61, while females have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.97 and 0.62 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 373 at an alpha level of 0.05; the calculated z-test of 3.756 is greater than the z-critical of 1.96. Along these lines, the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean rating score of male and female teachers on the extent the school social environment influences students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.4: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the mean ratings score of male and female teachers on the extent the school social environment influences students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	z-cal	Z-crit.	Remarks
Male	163	2.68	0.89	373	0.761	±1.96	Not Significant
Female	212	2.61	0.88	2			Accept H ₀ ₂ (z-cal. < z-crit.)
Total	375			375			

Table 4.4 revealed that males have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.68 and 0.89, while females have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.61 and 0.88 respectively. With a degree of freedom of 373 at an alpha level of 0.05; the calculated z-test of 0.761 is less than the z-critical of 1.96. Along these lines, the null hypothesis is accepted. By implication, there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent the school social environment influences students' drop out in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The Impact of School Physical Environment on Students' Dropout

The result showed that the school's physical environment has an impact on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State. Some of the school physical environment factors considered included; The fence in my school is not good, so students move out freely and get in contact with bad people that may influence dropout, dilapidated school buildings, inadequate classrooms and lockers/chairs, poor library/laboratory facilities, and overcrowded classrooms, The unkempt school physical environment is a great threat to students' safety. This means that for effective teaching and learning to occur and to prevent secondary school students from leaving due to poor school conditions, the physical environment of the school, which is an essential aspect of the school's structure and facilities, should be sufficient, comfortable, and should ultimately motivate students to stay in school. Also, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the impact of school physical environment on students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Supporting the findings are Taddese and Tadele (2019), who studied the Prevalence, Causes, and Prevention of Primary School Dropout in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. The research revealed that the causes of dropout included, among other factors, the unfavorable school environment and school authorities.

Extent The School Social Environment Influences Students' Dropout

The result revealed that the school social environment influences students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. These factors include; One of the reasons why students think of leaving the school is the issue of cultism in the school among students, the Negative attitude of some teachers in my school could make students drop out of school, Lack of social activities in my school could lead to dropout, corporate punishment may scare some students and so cause them to drop out of school. However, the male and female respondents disagree aggressiveness of our teachers makes students absent from the classroom at times causing poor performance which leads to dropout is not part of the influence of the school social environment on students' dropout in secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, there is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent the school social environment influences students' dropout in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study by Taddese and Tadele (2019) whose research delved into the

prevalence, causes, and preventive measures of primary school dropout in Gurage Zone, Ethiopia. It unveiled that in addition to other influencing factors, the reasons for dropout encompassed the adverse school environment and the interplay of behaviors and relationships among school authorities (principals and teachers) and students. These dynamics posed significant challenges for students within the school setting.

CONCLUSION

The physical environment in Nigeria is not anywhere all it ought to be as an environment particularly conducive to student comfort, necessary for students' ability to develop the appropriate attitudes, skills, and knowledge for responsible citizenship. An environment that is not truly accessible, not reasonably comfortable, not particularly stimulating to cognition, and not truly free of physical, biological, and chemical hazards generally clears the path for low-quality education, which is diametrically at variance with student achievement goals. The school environment holds a pivotal role in shaping the growth of children, which can be further broken down into physical and social aspects. The physical environment encompasses all the facilities that support effective teaching and learning, while the social environment refers to how the school setting influences and fosters interactions and relationships among all members, including management, staff, and students. A comprehensive study revealed that these factors contribute significantly to students dropping out of secondary schools in Rivers State. The study highlighted that all secondary school students in Rivers State encounter similar challenges within their school environment when striving to remain in school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made, based on the findings of this study:

1. The schools in Rivers State are in urgent need of improvement. Outdated and dilapidated classroom buildings must be refurbished and repainted to create a more welcoming and conducive learning environment. Additionally, providing adequate facilities is crucial to enhance the overall physical condition of these schools.
2. The school's social environment should be free from any form of abuse and violence, and instead, it should be a place where students feel cared for, valued, and respected. This environment should provide a strong support system, encourage mental wellness, create opportunities for physical activity and exercise, and foster mentorship and positive role modeling. These conditions will contribute to enhancing the overall well-being and happiness of the students, making them more likely to be engaged and successful in their educational journey.

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